

ETHICAL ETHNIC FASHION AND REPURCHASE INTENTION

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Abstract:

This research aims to develop new constructs and indicators needed to investigate customer repurchase intentions by determining the effect of ethical ethnic fashion, subjective norm, and attitude as mediating variables by applying the Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA). Data was collected by distributing online questionnaires to ethical ethnic fashion customers in several cities in Indonesia. A total of 230 questionnaires fulfilled the requirements, which were further analyzed using SEM analysis software in IBM SPSS-AMOS version 23. The overall model test results show a significant number. The findings showed that the trust in the ethical ethnic fashion, capable of maintaining sustainability affects individuals' positive attitudes, which impact repurchase intentions. The trust comes from the thorough product evaluation that affects the individuals' emotional feelings and trust in the closest people who give references. These two factors have a strong effect on shaping customer attitudes to repurchase ethical ethnic fashion. This research also helps ethnic fashion producers understand the importance of equating customers' perceptions of ethical concepts to increase potential customer satisfaction.

Keywords: Repurchase Intention, Attitude, Subjective Norm, Ethical Ethnic Fashion

INTRODUCTION

The trend of wearing ethnic clothing in Indonesia is increasingly widespread. Ethnic clothing made from traditional woven fabrics has dramatically reached fashion enthusiasts. This is indicated by the demand for textile and apparel markets. The sales proceeds contributed up to IDR. 127.43 trillion In 2021 is predicted to increase again in the years to come (Karnadi, 2022). One of the factors that cause the high demand for clothing with an ethnic touch is its modern appearance, which no longer seems old-fashioned. This is due to the innovation of local designers who are making a difference. In the hands of designers, ethnic clothes look much more fashionable, luxurious, and classy (Melati, 2022). Thus, ethnic fashion, which was still explicitly used for traditional ceremony celebrations a decade ago, can now be worn on any occasion by all ages (Ngantung, 2019).

Ethnic fashion is essential in preserving local wisdom so that cultural values passed down from ancestors are preserved (Hasbullah et al., 2022). In addition, to maintain the continuity of the nation's culture, this ethnic fashion also has a relationship with economic factors where these small industrial craftsmen also get a decent income to support their families (Effendi et al., 2019; Yusof et al., 2018). In general, these traditional weavers are women who pursue the profession as weavers to generate income; usually, the woven cloth will be accommodated by the entrepreneur and the entrepreneur who markets it (Djafar, 2014; Rodgers, 2011). Ethnic fashion, an ancestral cultural heritage totaling 33 fabrics from various provinces in Indonesia,

has been designed into modern ready-to-wear clothing (Nadya, 2021; Rahman, 2017). The uniqueness of this ethnic dress lies in the decorative style, which has a deep philosophical meaning that describes the spirit of life (Abdollah et al., 2016). This culturally valuable clothing is a product that shows one's ethnic identity; therefore, the tendency of consumers to wear ethnic clothing is due to feelings of pride in their ethnic identity which shows in their attitudes and behaviour (Valdez & López, 2019; Kim & Arthur, 2003; Liu & Xing, 2017).

In the previous decade, the development of ethnic fashion was not encouraging, many ethnic print fabrics were circulating in the market at lower prices, plus the lack of business capital, lack of promotion, and motives that were not varied made sales decline in the market. Thus, to boost sales, it is necessary to apply product differentiation in collaboration with designers. This collaboration is vital to show the potential of ancestral weaving with unique decorative patterns, now into elegant ready-to-wear clothing (Hapsari, 2015).

Interestingly, on the side of ethnic fashion, there are ethical elements such as the artistry and materials used. Materials from organic fibres that are environmentally friendly and the handmade process can suppress the process of accelerating production (Fletcher, 2010; Putri, 2021). Therefore, ethnic fashion is under the principle of sustainability which is currently in demand. The shift of consumer interest to ethical fashion is undoubtedly beneficial for the traditional fashion industry because consumers who are aware of a better future will choose sustainable fashion (Wijaya & Paramita, 2021).

Consumers demand ethical products that concern worker welfare, environmental conservation and animal welfare, all of which are contained ethnically. (Dissanayake et al., 2017; Stringer et al., 2020). These ethnic fashion respondents have a good level of education so that they are morally responsible for sustainability. (Adomaviciute, 2014; Haug & Busch, 2016; Jung & La, 2020).

Belief in ethical fashion has formed attitudes that have an impact on purchase intention (Sun, 2020). Consumer confidence is obtained after thoroughly evaluating this ethnic fashion (Fishbein & Ajzen, 1980) and finding several ethical factors. In addition, decorative patterns contain philosophical meanings, and if interpreted, they will become the life spirit of the wearer (Taourisia et al., 2012; Bahauddin et al., 2015; Yandri, 2014). This affects emotional attitudes, so wearing it will lead to pride (Kim & Arthur, 2003; C. Liu & Xing, 2017; Rodgers, 2011). The subjective component of the norm also influences attitudes through social pressure from those closest to them to buy this ethnic fashion (Fishbein & Ajzen, 1975). Furthermore, the satisfying experience after wearing this ethically ethnic fashion causes the intention to repurchase (Vignesh Karthik, 2017).

So far, studies on ethical fashion have focused on organic material issues such as repair, reuse or environment-friendly disposal and the textile handloom industry (Abdullah, 2021; Jung & La, 2020; Wan et al., 2017; Dissanayake et al., 2017), because there is no research linking ethnic fashion and ethical fashion at the same time. The ethnic component is important to study because the market is increasingly aware of its importance in developing trendy fashion (Liu & Xing, 2017). This is in line with the opinion (Kim & Arthur, 2003), which states the market

tends to return to fashion that prioritizes local wisdom. This opinion is also supported by (Mohamed Basil, 2013), which states that ethnicity is a product differentiation that fashion manufacturers are increasingly choosing because the market segment has grown significantly in recent years.

Therefore, the authors include the Ethical Ethnic Fashion variable as a novelty in this study. This research is an integrated process of developing a new, ethically ethnic fashion concept. This study aimed to investigate the characteristics of fashion, trust, and reference group and customer attitudes towards repurchase intention. This study was conducted to fill the gap by adding the concept of the theory of reasoned action (TRA), which focuses on attitude as a mediating variable. This research is also expected to contribute references for further in-depth research on ethical fashion.

RESEARCH MODEL AND HYPOTHESES

Repurchase Intention

Fishbein and Ajzen (1975) stated that TRA serves as a theoretical basis. This concept has become an essential reference in the field of social sciences (Bagozzi, 1992) due to its accuracy in predicting various behaviors (Shepherd & O'keefe, 1984). In the context of this research, TRA is related to purchase intention because it is one of the most important components in achieving a desirable purchasing behavior. Furthermore, it discusses the variable determinants such as attitude towards behavioral and subjective norm concerning behavior (Fishbein & Ajzen, 1975). It is also used as a mediating and independent variable and ethical ethnic fashion, which focuses on the intention to purchase environmentally-friendly fashion.

Ariffin et al. (2016) defined repurchase intention as the customer's desire to re-buy certain green products due to past satisfactory factors to obtain similar benefits. The previous research by (Nam et al., 2017) stated that consumers' perceptions of organic products are that they are comfortable to wear. It based on their experiences of buying sports clothes made of environmentally friendly materials. The research carried out by (Dissanayake et al., 2017) on consumers' purchasing intention of ethically processed ethnic fashion offers broader sustainability in boosting the global market with handicraft products, thereby improving the welfare of local artisans. Setiawan & Afrilinda (2020) stated that the essence of repurchasing second-hand fashion items is to ensure they are not thrown away, thereby becoming hazardous waste. It was further discovered that the consumers were emotionally satisfied, which led to the sustainability of the environment in the future.

Attitude

After a thorough evaluation, Fishbein & Ajzen (1975) defined attitude as a pleasant or unpleasant feeling toward a specific object. In accordance with TRA, it strongly influences purchase intention and attitude as a mediator between ethical ethnic fashion and subjective norm variables (Perry, 2016). Attitudes such as trust play an important role in making sustainable purchases (Coleman et al., 2011; Neumann et al., 2020). Preliminary research also discovered that a positive attitude towards environmentally friendly products affects consumers' purchase intention (Lang & Armstrong, 2018; Liu et al., 2020; Maichum et al., 2016; Nam et al., 2017; Stringer et al., 2020).

Jung & La (2020) confirmed that consumers' attitude toward ethical fashion is influenced by their emotional feelings, namely the moral norms within individuals. Meanwhile, Wan et al. (2017) stated that the intention to purchase recycled products is influenced by attitude to reduce the number of waste items. Adomaviciute (2014), and Shen et al. (2012) reported that environmental concerns, and social workers, bring about sustainability. It was concluded that the strong desire for a better future helps individuals prefer fashion products made from environmentally friendly materials. Therefore, it is hypothesized that attitude positively affects repurchase intention.

H₁: Attitude has a positive effect on repurchase intention.

Subjective Norm

According to Fishbein & Ajzen (1975), the subjective norm is the person's perception that important most people who are important to him think he or she should or should not perform the behavior in question. It plays an important role in influencing repurchase intention, which is triggered by closest relatives and friends (Massoro & Adewale, 2019). Mishra et al. (2014) also stated that subjective norm significantly motivates individuals to exhibit their behavioral intention. Based on the aforementioned definition, it was concluded that the reference to closest relatives and friends is a strong factor that influences the individual's positive attitude towards the intention to repurchase ethical ethnic fashion.

The preliminary research by (Fang et al., 2017; Karjaluoto & Leppäniemi, 2013; Perry, 2016; Tarkiainen & Sundqvist, 2005) confirmed that individuals' trust in their closest relatives and friends' suggestions tend to affect their attitudes, which impact on purchase intention. Furthermore, Nam et al. (2017) examined environmentally friendly sportswear and discovered that the references provided did not merely act as a factor influence purchasing decisions but tend to trigger a positive attitude toward environmental sustainability. This is because the reference group is perceived as a community of environmentalists who provide affirmative information regarding the impact of buying environmentally friendly sportswear. The norm or values instilled in a family also affect good attitudes as well as has an impact on behavior (Maichum et al., 2016). The closest people who emphasize these references also belong to the green-conscious community, there by being able to pressure these individuals easily. This implies those who completely believe all this information develop a positive attitude that has an impact on purchase intention (Ham et al., 2015; Hasan & Suciarto, 2020; Jain, 2020; Peña-

García et al., 2020; Prayoga et al., 2018). Therefore, it is hypothesized that subjective norm affects attitude and repurchase intention.

H₂: Subjective norm has a positive effect on attitude.

H₃: Subjective norm has a positive effect on repurchase intention.

H₄: Subjective norm has a positive effect on repurchase intention through attitude.

Ethical Ethnic Fashion

Chattaraman & Lennon (2008) defined ethnic fashion as some sorting clothing that is strongly used to identify certain ethnicities, and it has characteristics that match the diverse cultures (Kim & Arthur, 2003; Liu & Xing, 2017; Quin, 2011). One prominent feature of ethnic fashion is that it is traditionally processed using handloom weaving equipment (Dissanayake et al., 2017; Rodgers, 2011; Yandri, 2014; Yusof et al., 2018). The benefits obtained to aid in maintaining traditional crafts' heritage value (Chai-Arayalert et al., 2021; Sharmin & Hossain, 2020; Zakriya et al., 2017).

Ethnic fashion also has a classic design that is bound to always remain in vogue and used for decades (Djafar, 2014; Rodgers, 2011). This tends to prevent rapid changes, excessive consumption, and early disposal of products (Niinimäki, 2011), as well as educate the public not to be consumptive in shopping (Carey & Cervellon, 2014; Fletcher, 2010; Henninger et al., 2016; McLaren & McLauchlan, 2015; Sustainable Markets, 2015; Watson & Yan, 2013).

Another advantage is that ethnic fashion produced with high-quality raw fabrics has strong durability. Generally, organic materials such as cotton, silk, gold, and metallic silver threads (Djafar, 2014) are not considered harmful to the environment because these are usually recycled, reused, and redesigned (Vindrola-Padros & Johnson, 2020; Yu & Lee, 2019). Meanwhile, the remaining fabric tends to be utilized for various accessories (Dissanayake et al., 2017). The positive impact of this method is to reduce waste items maximally. (Hassan et al., 2022) (Yadav et al., 2021) (Abdel-Shafy & Mansour, 2018) (Chen & Lee, 2020) (Lamba et al., 2021).

The workforce comprises experienced local craftsmen, who work under safe and conducive conditions. Therefore, the traditional weaving industry is in accordance with ethical principles to maintain sustainability. This is realized by adopting a balanced approach to promote the long-term growth and increase local production (Fletcher, 2010; Moorhouse, 2020; Ertekin & Atik, 2015). At the same time, it even tends to promote zero-waste, fair trade, and sweatshop-free to influence sustainability at large. All principles of ethical ethnic fashion affect the individuals' emotional feelings, which positively impact purchase intention (Wan et al., 2017). Therefore, it affects attitude and repurchase intention.

H₅: Ethical ethnic fashion has a positive effect on attitude.

H₆: Ethical ethnic fashion has a positive effect on repurchase intention.

H₇: Ethical ethnic fashion positively affects repurchase intention through attitude.

RESEARCH MODEL

The research framework employed the TRA concept to identify the direct relationship between ethical ethnic fashion, subjective norm, attitude, and repurchase intention. Furthermore, an indirect relationship exists between ethical ethnic fashion, subjective norm, and attitude-mediated repurchase intention. As shown in figure 1

Figure 1 : Research Model

METHODOLOGY

Measurement Variabel

The question provided in the questionnaires related to the research in term of 4 variables i.e. (1) Variable of repurchase intention consisting of five 5queries: I intend to buy ethical ethnic fashion in the future; I plan to purchase more green products rather than normal products; I will make an effort to buy green fashion in the future; I will try to buy ethical ethnic fashion in the future; I intend strongly to buy ethical ethnic fashion. These questions, moreover, were modified by (Fishbein & Ajzen, 1975; Nam et al., 2017)in their previous researches. (2) Variable of attitude consists of six questions namely: I think that purchasing ethical ethnic fashion is safe; I think that purchasing ethical fashion is good idea; I think that wear ethical ethnic fashion is wise; I think that wear ethical ethnic fashion is favourable; I feel happy to wear ethical ethnic fashion; Furthermore, the last question: I fell strong liking wear ethical ethnic fashion,

The modified question from (Fishbein & Ajzen, 1975; Maichum et al., 2016; Taylor & Todd, 1995). (3) Variable ethical ethnic fashion consist of :Worker welfare; Environmental concern; Animal welfare; Adherence to the Islamic faith; Philosophy value; Shown ethnic identity. The modifications from (Chattaraman & Lennon, 2008; Leigh, 1989; Stringer et al., 2020). (4) Variable of Subjective Norms consists of six queries: My designer would think that I should wear ethical fashion; Generally speaking, I want to do what my designer think I should do; My family, think that I should wear ethical ethnic fashion; Generally speaking, I want to do what my family think I should do; My friend, think that I should wear ethical ethnic fashion;

Generally speaking, I want to do what my friend think I should do. The modifications from (Tarkiainen & Sundqvist, 2005; Taylor & Todd, 1995). Table 1 below shows the measurement of variable

Table 1: Measurement of Variable

Variable	Questionnaire Items	References
Repurchase Intention	I intend to buy ethical ethnic fashion in the future	Modifications From (Fishbein & Ajzen, 1975; Nam et al., 2017)
	I plan to purchase more green products rather than normal products	
	I will make an effort to buy green fashion in the future	
	I will try to buy ethical ethnic fashion in the future	
	I intend strongly to buy ethical ethnic fashion	
Attitude	I think that purchasing ethical ethnic fashion is safe	Modifications from (Fishbein & Ajzen, 1975, p.342; Maichum et al., 2016; Taylor & Todd, 1995)
	I think that wear ethical ethnic fashion is good idea	
	I think that wear ethical ethnic fashion is wise	
	I think that purchasing ethical ethnic fashion is favorable	
	I feel happy to wear ethical ethnic fashion	
I fell strong liking wear ethical ethnic fashion		
Ethical Ethnic Fashion	Worker welfare	Modifications from (Chattaraman & Lennon, 2008; Leigh, 1989; Stringer et al., 2020)
	Environmental concern	
	Animal welfare	
	Adherence to the Islamic faith	
	Philosophy value	
Subjective Norms	Shown ethnic identity	Modifications from (Tarkiainen & Sundqvist, 2005; Taylor & Todd, 1995)
	My designer would think that I should wear ethical etchnic fashion	
	Generally speaking, I want to do what my designer think I should do	
	My family, think that I should wear ethical etchnic fashion	
	Generally speaking, I want to do what my family think I should do	
	My friend, think that I should wear ethical etchnic fashion	
Generally speaking, I want to do what my friend think I should do		

Data Collection

The target population is all Indonesians, and respondents are ethical ethnic fashion customers who have made more than one purchase. According to Aeni (2021), Indonesia consists of 34 provinces with 33 types of woven fabrics from all these regions (Rahman, 2017). Therefore, virtually all of the are involved in traditional woven fabrics.

Several designers have converted this ethnic fabric into the hallmark of their fashion collections. With their creativity, they have succeeded in processing traditional weaving that resembles contemporary formal ready-to-wear clothes that tend to be mixed and matched with other materials and accessories. This causes wider usage, which impacts increasing demand for ethical ethnic fashion.

This research adopted a purposive sampling technique where the sample acquired are based on certain considerations to obtain more representative data (Sugiyono, 2019). The questionnaire contains a list of questions related to the research variables, compiled in a Google form and distributed to respondents online. This was assisted by the author's relations, who are domiciled in several provinces in Indonesia. The respondents were referred in accordance with the criteria stated in the questionnaire. A 7-point Likert scale test was performed to measure how strongly they agreed or disagreed with the given questions (Sekaran & Bougie, 2016). The sample size for the SEM model is between 100 to 200, realized by multiplying the number of indicators by 5 or 10 (Ferdinand, 2014).

Demographic Information of the Data

A total of 255 respondents participated in the survey, but only 230 people fulfilled the requirements, while 25 were data outliers. Of 230 customers, 208 (90.28%) were females and 22 (9.71%) males. Furthermore, those aged between 31 to 36 years, 37 to 42 years, 43 to 48 years, as well as 49 years and above are 49 (21%), 83 (36%), 73 (32%), and 25 (11%), respectively. The education level of respondents include 17 (9.71%) Diploma 3, 29 (57%) undergraduate (S1), 72 (41.14%) graduate (S2), and 57 (32.57%) postgraduate (S3). Meanwhile, based on occupation, 67 (29%) were civil servants, 30 (13%) private employees, 41 (18%) SOE workers, 59 (26%) entrepreneurs, and 33 (14%) housewives. as shown in the table below.

Table 2: Demographic Information of Survey Respondents

Classification		Frekwensi	Ratio (%)
Gender	Females	208	90
	Males	22	10
Total		230	100
Age	31 - 36 years	49	21
	37 - 42 years	83	36
	43 - 48 years	73	32
	49 and over	25	11
Total		230	100
Education level	Diploma graduates	22	10
	University graduates	38	16
	Graduate school graduates	95	41
	Doctor Graduates	75	32
Total		230	100
Occupation	Civil servants	67	29
	Private employees	30	13
	SOE workers	41	18
	Entrepreneurs	59	26
	Housewives	33	14
Total		230	100

Data Analysis

The data analysis techniques employed in this research were descriptive and verification. Descriptive analysis was carried out to assess the respondents' demographic profile and the internal consistency of the constructs. The verification analysis was performed with SEM (Structural Equation Modelling) to verify the relationship between ethical ethnic fashion, subjective norm, attitude, and repurchase intention. Additionally, the SEM analysis software utilized was IBM SPSS-AMOS version 23.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Analysis Results of Reliability and Validity

This analysis involves determining the loading factor, composite reliability (CR), and average variance extract (AVE). The loading factor obtained was from 0.721 to 0.924, and according to Hair et al. (2017), it and composite reliability need to be greater than 0.70, as shown in Table 3. Meanwhile, AVE and CR were with in 0.804 to 0.877 and 0.913 to 0.912, respectively. This indicates the measurement analysis results were valid and reliable(Hair et al., 2019). This research also evaluated the discriminant validity (Henseler et al., 2015) Heterotrait-Monotrait (HTMT). Its value from the lowest to the highest was 0.503 to 0.817. This is in accordance

with the HTMT limits of 0.85 and 0.90 in (Kline, 2015). The HTMT results are shown in table 4, which depicts that the discriminant validity value is acceptable.

Table 3: Results of Reliability and Validity

Construct	Items	Factor Loading	Average	CR
Repurchase Intention	RI1	0,747	0,813	0,936
	RI2	0,832		
	RI3	0,765		
	R4	0,801		
	RI5	0,869		
Attitude	A1	0,803	0,804	0,913
	A2	0,736		
	A3	0,874		
	A4	0,815		
	A5	0,721		
	A6	0,805		
Ethical Ethnic Fashion	EEF1	0,873	0,817	0,952
	EEF2	0,924		
	EEF3	0,835		
	EEF4	0,842		
	EEF5	0,816		
	EEF6	0,879		
Subjective Norm	SN1	0,802	0,814	0,971
	SN2	0,768		
	SN3	0,739		
	SN4	0,831		
	SN5	0,857		
	SN6	0,870		

Table:4 The Results of Heterotrait-Mentrait (HTMT) Test

	Repurchase Intention	Attitude	Ethical Ethnic Fashion	Subjective Norm
Repurchase Intention	0,514			
Attitude	0,723	0,652		
Ethical Ethnic Fashion	0,675	0,626	0,514	
Subjective Norm	0,767	0,875	0,532	0,503

Table 5: Results of the Struktural Model

	Hypothesized Path	Estimates	Standardized Coefficients	CR	P	Decision
H ₁	Attitude <--- Ethical Ethnic Fashion	0,628	,149	4,289	***	Supported
H ₂	Attitude<--- Subjective Norm	0,727	,137	5,302	***	Supported
H ₃	Repurchase Intention <-- -- Ethical Ethnic Fashion	0,438	,155	2,833	***	Supported
H ₄	Repurchase Intention <-- -- Attitude	0,469	,130	3,065	***	Supported
H ₅	Repurchase Intention <-- --Subjective Norm	0,337	,148	3,172	***	Supported

Notes: $\chi^2 = 98,673$, GFI = 0.874, AGFI = , TLI = 0,927, CFI = 0.923, RMSEA = 0,076, Normedchisq/CMIN = 1.783,

*p < 0.05; **p < 0.01, *** p<0.001

Figure 2: Hypothesis Testing

Analysis of Structural Model

Based on Table 5, the proposed model has 5 structural paths with the following variables: the effects of ethical ethnic fashion and subjective norms on attitude have estimated values of 0.628 and 0.727 with a significance level of 0.001. Meanwhile, the effects of ethical ethnic fashion, attitude, and subjective norms on repurchase intention have estimated values of 0.438, 0.337, and 0.469, with a significance level of 0.001. Based on these results, the research variables influence each other, as proven by the significant probability value of 0.001. This value is less than the significant level (α), which is determined at 0.05 and C.R. > 2.0, indicating the hypothesis is accepted. The effect of each exogenous variable on the endogenous ones also has a positive coefficient of 0.149, 0.137, 0.155, 0.130, and 0.148. This shows that they are mediated by attitude and have a positive and significant effect on each other. It was concluded

that all hypotheses are accepted. Additionally, from H1 to H5 obtain Goodness of Fit Test values, such as Chi-Square/ $\chi^2 = 98.673$, GFI = 0.874, AGFI = 0.847, TLI = 0.927, CFI = 0.923, RMSEA = 0.076, and Normedchisq/ $C_{MIN} = 1.783$. Overall, these values are good, and it was reported that the model had fulfilled all the requirements.

Figure 2 shows that ethical ethnic fashion and subjective norms positively and significantly affect attitude and repurchase intention. Likewise, the attitude has a positive and significant effect on repurchase intention. This finding is consistent with previous research on the subjective norm that affects attitude, and it has an impact on the intention to purchase sustainable products (Brandão & da Costa, 2021; Chu, 2018; Diyah & Wijaya, 2017; Lionço et al., 2019; Saleki et al., 2019; Saricam & Okur, 2019; Zhao et al., 2019). Furthermore, a satisfying experience after using the products leads to repeat purchases (Chuang & Chiu, 2018; Lam et al., 2016; Saputra et al., 2020; Wijaya & Paramita, 2021).

Ethical ethnic fashion, which is regarded as a new variable in this research, has not been investigated, hence, it was not included in the findings. However, after the test, it was discovered to have a positive and significant relationship between attitude and repurchase intention, as shown in Figure 2. Ethical ethnic fashion and subjective norms, directly and indirectly, affect consumers' repurchase intention, as stated in previous research (Liu & Xing, 2017; Nam et al., 2017; Perry, 2016). In relation to indirectly influencing repurchase intention, these two variables are mediated by attitude.

Ethnic fashion as an economic, cultural asset does not only serve as a means of livelihood for craftsmen, and also maintains the value of local wisdom. It is expected to have a competitive advantage in facing new economic challenges, resulting in sustainable growth. Similarities were discovered in preliminary research (Méndez-Picazo et al., 2021; Mensah, 2019) that sustainable development triggers dynamic economic growth and social justice and is sensitive to cultural aspects.

Along with preserving culturally valuable fashion, the most basic factor is the presence of an ethical element. Moreover, an ethical ethnic fashion is the choice of consumers due to the trust in better sustainability. In this research, all the respondents are highly educated and knowledgeable about the impact of ethical fashion. Suggestions made by closest relatives and friends also have a strong influence in motivating purchasing decisions. An individual's integrity is due to a good upbringing in the family, which aid in developing certain attitudes that are reflected in their behavior. Coakley & Kates (2013), Ferguson & Ostmann (2018), and Jung & La (2020) also emphasized that moral values are the main attributes that trigger response to ethical fashion. These norms also make a person voluntarily perform useful deeds for the good of others.

Sometimes, an individual is also faced with a dilemma, such as paying a high price for ethical fashion products while there are similar items with relatively cheaper prices manufactured in sweatshops. In circumstances where individuals follow the *ceteris paribus* preference, they certainly pay a low price rather than a high one. However, there is a sense of admiration and pride because this fashion displays ethnic culture, plus an additional process that leads to a

feeling of likeness. In TRA, attitude as an affective dimension (Fishbein & Ajzen, 1975, 1980) is an individual's emotional feeling towards stimuli after thorough evaluation. This is natural for everyone, besides, it is an act of defense against injustice and support for sustainability. An individual with integrity certainly has a strong intention to make appropriate decisions on issues regarding sustainability.

CONCLUSION

The results obtained from this research show that the main factor that favors this fashion sense is the trust in ethical concepts regarding the material used and the manufacturing process. The consequences towards sustainability have led to the development of a positive attitude, indicating the consideration of ethical ethnic fashion is ideal. References made by closest relatives and friends are also related to repurchase intention. Some research on environmentally friendly fashion has been carried out; however, those that discuss cultural heritage fashion are limited, whereas traditional woven fabrics are a completely sustainable system. This research combines two concepts, namely ethnic and ethic in addition, interesting results in the form of similarities were found in one object.

Managerial Implication

This research provides several managerial implications. First, ethical ethnic fashion has formed a solid foundation for increased satisfaction and repurchase intention. Due to the expertise of these woven fabric craftsmen and local fashion designers, they appear in contemporary styles and are suitable for use on various occasions. This condition has dispelled the old assumption that such clothes seem stiff and are only suitable for traditional occasions. As an ethnic fashion that boosts sustainability, customers feel the need to support it, there by ensuring that this fashion is continuously produced in the future. Second, the majority feel happy after wearing these attires. The result is a tendency to repurchase and recommend them to friends and family.

Therefore, customer satisfaction is a priority for producers. In circumstances, where customers have unpleasant experiences, there is a high probability that their disappointment is bound to be conveyed to other people. The main attribute that needs to be understood by producers is to maintain customer satisfaction. This factor is also bound to affect attitude, which impacts repurchase intention. Third, Indonesia has a variety of traditional woven attires that differ in each region. These fabrics are a unique fashion innovation, and it is attractive to customers. They even have some ethnic clothing from various regions worn at formal and non-formal events. These customers also promote ethnic clothing, making this fashion popular among the upper-middle class. Another added value is hand-processed with natural materials that provide a relaxing effect for the wearer, accompanied by various decorative patterns and attractive colors. The impact is that the selling value of this fashion is getting better, thereby increasing the craftsmen' income and preserving local culture. It is also exhibited at international events and broadens the market where local cultural products are sold. In general, those abroad purchase ethically processed fashion, making it a profitable export commodity.

Limitations and Future Research

This research is only limited to ethical ethnic fashion in almost all provinces in Indonesia. Other products in traditional contexts popular among the people are their locally prepared foods, medicines, herbs, and herbal cosmetic care products. These items are ideal for curing diseases and nourishing the body, are safe for consumption, and do not harm the environment. Furthermore, only quantitative approach was adopted, therefore, future research is recommended to use mixed methods. This research only applied TRA with attitude as a mediating variable. Therefore, it is also recommended that the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) and Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) approaches, which are the developed TRA, are applied.

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